

ID-1200

COMPARISON OF THE SEAWATER DURABILITY OF CARBON- AND GLASS-POLYMER COMPOSITES

A. Kootsookos¹, A.P. Mouritz¹ and N.A. St John²

¹ *The Sir Lawrence Wackett Centre for Aerospace Design Technology,
Department of Aerospace Engineering, RMIT University,
GPO Box 2476V, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia 3001.*

² *Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory,
Defence Science and Technology Organisation,
GPO Box 4331, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia 3001.*

SUMMARY: The long-term seawater durability of glass/polyester, carbon/polyester, glass/vinyl ester and carbon/vinyl ester composites that are used in marine structures are compared in a preliminary study. The composites are virtually identical in terms of fabrication processing, dimensions, thickness and fibre volume fraction, and this allowed the effects of fibre type (ie. glass vs. carbon) and resin type (ie. polyester vs. vinyl ester) on durability to be determined. When immersed in seawater at a temperature of 30°C, the carbon composites display better durability than the glass composites. Weight change measurements show that the amount of moisture absorbed by carbon/polyester and carbon/vinyl ester composites is lower compared with glass/polyester and glass/vinyl ester materials. It is speculated that the difference is due to a greater loss of unreacted polymer from the resin matrix of the carbon composites. The water absorbed by the carbon composites did not affect significantly the flexural modulus and flexural strength whereas the flexural properties of the glass composites declined slowly when immersed for long periods in seawater. Water absorption also appears to affect the stability of mode I delamination cracks in the glass/polyester composite.

KEYWORDS: Carbon Composite, Glass Composite, Durability, Seawater Absorption, Mechanical Properties, Interlaminar Fracture

INTRODUCTION

Glass reinforced polyester composites are used often in marine craft and are used occasionally in offshore oil drilling platforms because of their low cost, light-weight, high strength and excellent corrosion resistance. A wide variety of marine craft are made of glass/polyester composites, including kayaks, canoes, fishing trawlers, patrol boats and naval minehunting ships. Glass/polyester is also used in the superstructure, masts and radomes of some large steel ships and in the non-pressure hull casing, sonar domes and masts of submarines [1,2]. The applications of glass/polyester composites on offshore drilling platforms include deck grates, low-pressure pipes and tanks [3]. Glass reinforced vinyl ester composites are also used in marine craft and offshore platforms, although usually in high-performance structures such as racing yachts and power-boats [1]. Other types of polymers that are used in glass reinforced composites for marine structures include epoxy and phenolic resins. However, over 90% of all marine composite structures are made with glass/polyester and glass/vinyl ester materials.

A drawback with using glass/polyester and glass/vinyl ester composites in large marine structures is their low Young's modulus. The bending modulus of these composites is typically below 40 MPa because of the low stiffness of glass fibres. The low modulus makes it difficult to build ultra-light racing yachts from thin glass composites and it is extremely challenging to construct glass composite ships longer than about 70 meters with adequate hull girder stiffness. Another problem is that seawater is absorbed by glass reinforced composites, which degrades the resin matrix, glass-to-resin interface, and attacks the glass fibres. This

damage can cause reductions to the mechanical and impact properties of glass reinforced composites when immersed in seawater for a long time [4-7]. For reasons such as these, many light-weight racing yachts are built using carbon reinforced composites which have much higher stiffness than glass/polyester and glass/vinyl laminates. Large ship builders are currently assessing the feasibility of building mid-sized naval vessels with carbon reinforced composites, and the Royal Swedish Navy recently launched the first all-carbon composite corvette that is 72 meters long [2]. Carbon composites are also being considered for use in mooring tendons, drill risers and tubes on offshore drilling platforms [3].

One concern with the use of carbon reinforced composites in marine structures is their long-term durability in seawater. Composite marine structures can be immersed continuously in seawater for several years, and it is common for some composite ships to be in seawater for over 20 years. While a considerable amount of information is available on the seawater durability of glass/polyester and glass/vinyl ester composites because of their use in marine structures over many years [4-7], much less is known about the long-term durability of carbon reinforced composites in seawater.

The aim of this paper is to present a preliminary study comparing the durability, degradation mechanisms and mechanical properties of glass/polyester and glass/vinyl ester composites against carbon/polyester and carbon/vinyl ester composites in seawater. The materials were immersed in seawater at a temperature of 30°C, which is about the maximum water temperature off the coast of northern Australia during the summer season. The rate and amount of water uptake is compared between the composites, and the effect of moisture absorption on the flexural properties and interlaminar fracture toughness are assessed.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Composite Materials

The glass/polyester and glass/vinyl ester composites were virtually identical in every respect (eg. fabrication technique, glass reinforcement, fibre volume content) except for the composition of the resin matrix. Both materials were made with four plies of an E-glass plain woven fabric supplied by Fibre Glass International Pty. Ltd., Australia. The fabric had an average filament diameter of 12 μm and an areal weight of 0.329 kg/m^2 . The glass fibres were coated with an emulsion-based sizing agent by the glass manufacturer to promote good chemical adhesion with the resin matrix. The resin used in the glass/polyester composite was an isophthalic polyester resin (Synolite 0288-T-1) supplied by Dulux Australia. The polyester was promoted with 2.1 parts per hundred (pph) (by weight) of 6% cobalt (II) 2-ethylhexanoate solution and catalysed with 1.7 pph of 25% methyl ethyl ketone peroxide solution. The glass/vinyl ester contained a vinyl ester resin (Derakane 411-350) supplied by Dow Chemicals that was promoted with 0.5 pph of a cobalt octoate solution and catalysed with 1.5 pph of 40% methyl ethyl ketone peroxide in dimethyl phthalate solution. Both composites were fabricated using the wet hand lay-up process into flat panels with a thickness of 1.5 ± 0.1 mm. The volume fraction of glass fibres in the two composites was identical at 0.31 ± 0.01 . After fabrication, the glass reinforced composites were cured at room temperature for several weeks before being immersed in seawater. The composites were cured at room temperature because most large marine composite structures are cured under ambient conditions.

The carbon/polyester and carbon/vinyl ester composites were nearly identical to the glass composites except for the type of fibre reinforcement. The carbon composites were made containing four plies of a plain woven carbon fabric supplied by Colan Pty. Ltd. The carbon fabric had the same plain weave pattern as the glass fabric. The carbon fabric had an areal weight of 0.195 kg/m^2 , and the carbon filaments were ~ 7 μm in diameter which is slightly thinner than the glass fibres. The carbon fibres were coated with an epoxy-based size rather

than the emulsion size used on the glass fibres. The polyester and vinyl ester resins used in the carbon composites were the same as those used in the glass composites. The fabrication technique, curing conditions and dimensions of the carbon composites were also the same as the glass composites. The fibre volume fraction of the carbon/polyester and carbon/vinyl ester composites was the same at 0.33 ± 0.02 , which is nearly identical to the fibre content of the two glass composites. The composition and physical properties of the glass and carbon composites are compared in table 1.

The degree of resin cure to the composites was determined using differential scanning calorimetry before being immersed in seawater, and for the different materials it was 88-89%. The composites are significantly undercured because they were cured at room temperature. This was done because most marine structures made of composite materials are cured under ambient conditions without an elevated temperature postcure. As a result, the polyester and vinyl ester matrices contain significant amounts of unreacted chemical species from the resin, promoter and catalyst.

Table 1. Properties of the composites.

Property	Glass/ Polyester	Carbon/ Polyester	Glass/ Vinyl Ester	Carbon/ Vinyl Ester
Fibre Volume Fraction	0.32	0.35	0.30	0.32
Density (g/cm ³)	1.53	1.37	1.62	1.29
Thickness (mm)	1.6	1.3	1.5	1.4
Original Mass ¹ (g)	36.8961	24.8285	35.0100	26.0751
Degree of Cure	88%	89%	89%	88%

1. Original sample mass for panel size of 120 mm by 120 mm.

SeaWater Durability and Mechanical Property Tests

Glass and carbon reinforced composite panels (measuring 120 mm by 120 mm) were immersed in a bath of seawater with a salinity content of about 2.9%. The bath temperature was controlled at $30\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The panels were withdrawn from the bath at regular intervals to measure the weight change to within an accuracy of 100 μg . The weight change measurements are used to determine the rate of moisture uptake. Composite panels were also withdrawn at different periods to determine changes to the flexural properties and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. Immediately after being withdrawn from the bath, the flexural modulus and strength was determined in quarter-point loading according to ASTM D790M (method 2) specifications [8]. Double cantilever beam (DCB) tests were performed in close accordance to ASTM D5528 to determine the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness [9]. Both the mode I strain energy release rate for crack initiation (G_{Ii}) and crack propagation (G_{Ic}) were measured in the DCB tests. DCB tests were only performed on the glass/polyester composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of immersion time on the weight gained by the glass/polyester and carbon/polyester composites cured at room temperature is shown in figure 1. In this figure the weight gain is normalised to the original weight fraction of resin in the composite. The profile of the water uptake curves for the composites are similar with increasing immersion time. The curves increase rapidly when the composites are first immersed in seawater because of the rapid absorption of moisture. After being immersed for about 4 days^{1/2} the weight gained by the composites reaches a maximum value, indicating that the materials are saturated with moisture. Increasing the immersion time beyond 4 days^{1/2} causes a gradual decline in the mass change curves.

Liao et al. [10] suggest that when moisture uptake curves have the profile shown in figure 1 it is indicative of long-term irreversible chemical and/or physical degradation of the composite. The microstructures of the glass/polyester and carbon/polyester composites were examined using scanning electron microscopy after being immersed for a long time in seawater (after 10 days^{1/2}) to determine whether the materials were physically degraded. No physical damage to the composites was observed, such as debonding of fibres from the polyester matrix that has been observed in some other types of composites when immersed in water. Because the polyester-based composites show no signs of physical damage, the gradual decline to the water uptake curves at long immersion times is probably caused by an irreversible chemical process. It is well known that isophthalic polyester resins undergo hydrolysis of the ester groups when immersed in seawater [11], and this is probably responsible for the gradual decline in the water uptake curves at long immersion times.

Fig. 1. Effect of immersion time on the mass change of the glass/polyester and carbon/polyester composites in the room temperature cured condition.

It is possible that other chemical degradation processes also contribute to the gradual decline to the water uptake curves of the polyester-based composite at long immersion times. To study these possible processes further, polyester-based composite samples were post-cured at elevated temperature (100°C for two hours) so that the resin matrix was fully cured, and then immersed in seawater. The effect of the degree of resin cure on the water uptake curves for the glass/polyester and carbon/polyester composites are shown in figure 2. The curves for the composites in the room temperature cured condition that are shown in figure 1 (where the polymer cure reaction is 88-89% complete) are re-plotted in figure 2 against curves for the composites in the fully cured condition (where the cure reaction is nearly 100% complete). It is seen that the room temperature cured composites gained less weight than the fully cured samples. A similar effect of resin under-cure on moisture uptake measurements has been observed by Boinard et al. [12], and it was attributed to the leaching out of unreacted polymer into seawater causing a weight loss. A similar degradation mechanism may also be occurring in the glass and carbon reinforced composites, with unreacted resin, promoter and catalyst being leached from the polyester matrix.

It is also seen in figure 2 that a greater reduction in the water uptake curves occurred for the carbon reinforced composites. This effect indicates that the carbon reinforcement may affect the degree of resin cure. This effect has also been observed by Seddon [13] for carbon/polyester composites, however the mechanism responsible for this process is not known. The fully cured glass reinforced polyester composite is also seen to absorb more water than the fully cured carbon reinforced composite and this behaviour has been attributed by Gellert et al. [7] to additional water uptake at the fibre-resin interface.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. Mass change during seawater immersion of (a) glass/polyester and (b) carbon/polyester composites cured at room temperature and fully postcured.

Water uptake curves for the glass/vinyl ester and carbon/vinyl ester composites in the room temperature cured condition are compared in figure 3. The curves for both composites increase sharply when first immersed in seawater due to the rapid absorption of moisture. After the initial rapid uptake, the composites are seen to continue to steadily adsorb more water at a slower rate. This is different to the behaviour of the polyester-based composites (shown in figure 1) that experience a steady decrease in weight after saturation. The difference is probably due to the much greater resistance of vinyl ester resins to hydrolytic degradation compared to polyester resins [11].

Figure 4 shows water uptake curves for the glass/vinyl ester and carbon/vinyl ester composites in the room temperature and fully cured conditions. The composites in the fully cured condition were post-cured at 120°C for two hours before being immersed in seawater. It is seen that the initial behaviour is similar to that observed for the polyester-based composites in that the room temperature cured carbon reinforced composite shows a significantly reduced weight gain compared to the fully cured composite and the glass reinforced composite. This suggests that the leaching out of unreacted polymer is increased through the use of the carbon reinforcement, although the reason for this has not yet been determined.

Fig. 3. Effect of immersion time on the mass change of the glass/vinyl and carbon/vinyl ester composites in the room temperature cured condition.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Mass change during seawater immersion of (a) glass/vinyl ester and (b) carbon/vinyl ester composites cured at room temperature and fully postcured.

The effect of seawater immersion on the flexural modulus and strength of the composites in the room temperature cured condition is shown in figure 5. (Flexural modulus data for the carbon/vinyl ester composite is not reported). Despite considerable scatter in the data, there is no significant reduction to the flexural properties of the carbon reinforced composites. There appears to be a small reduction to the properties of the glass reinforced composites with increasing immersion time, however this cannot be stated conclusively because of the large variability in the data. The results for the glass composites agree with other durability studies [7] that found the flexural properties of glass/polyester and glass/vinyl ester composites are reduced slightly (typically less than 20%) when immersed for long periods in seawater. It appears, therefore, that the flexural properties of glass reinforced composites are reasonably stable in seawater whereas carbon reinforced composites are highly stable. It also appears that the gradual drop in weight of the polyester-based composites at long immersion times due to hydrolysis and loss of unreacted chemicals from the resin does not have a significant effect on the flexural properties.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 5. Effect of immersion time on the (a&b) flexural modulus and (c&d) flexural strength of the composites. The error bars represent one standard deviation in the measured properties.

The effect of seawater immersion on the toughness of the resin matrix and fibre-resin interface of the glass/polyester composite was assessed by mode I interlaminar fracture toughness testing. (Fracture toughness studies on the other composites are in progress, and will be reported in a future paper). Figure 6 shows the effect of seawater immersion time on the initiation energy (G_{ii}) and propagation energy (G_{lc}) for mode I interlaminar crack growth in the composite. Also shown is the weight change curve for the composite. The critical strain energy for crack initiation remains relatively constant with increasing immersion time to 4 day^{1/2}, and then for longer times the crack initiation energy increases steadily. The crack initiation energy is expected to be unchanged for short immersion times because moisture has not had adequate time to diffuse from the specimen surface to the crack initiation site located at the mid-plane of the specimen. The water uptake curve indicates that the composite is saturated when the immersion time reaches 4 days^{1/2}, and it is at this time that the crack initiation energy begins to increase. Fracture toughness specimens have a resin-rich region at

the tip of the pre-crack that can have a strong effect on the crack initiation energy. It is possible that moisture absorbed by this resin-rich region caused some plasticisation that increased the strain energy for crack initiation.

The crack propagation energies shown in figure 6b reveal that seawater immersion does not affect the interlaminar fracture toughness for long cracks. However, the amount of scatter of the G_{Ic} values increases considerably for immersion times longer than about 4 days^{1/2}, indicating that the crack growth process becomes less stable due to the absorption of water.

Fig. 6. Effect of immersion time on the mode I (a) crack initiation energy and (b) crack propagation energy for the glass/polyester composite in the room temperature cured condition. The error bars represent one standard deviation in the measured strain energy values.

CONCLUSIONS

The type of fibre, resin and degree of resin cure affect the durability of glass and carbon reinforced composites in seawater. Glass composites are less stable in seawater than carbon composites. In addition, polyester-based composites are less durable in seawater than vinyl ester-based composites, and this is due to the susceptibility of the polyester resin to hydrolysis.

Some degradation of the polyester- and vinyl ester-based composites appears to occur by the leaching out of unreacted chemicals from the resin matrix into seawater, and the extent of this process increases with the amount of under-curing of the resin. The room temperature cured carbon reinforced composites appear to experience the leaching process to a greater extent than glass reinforced composites, though the reason for this is unclear. These degradation processes appear to have no effect on the flexural properties of carbon composites and appear to cause only a slight reduction to the flexural properties of glass composites. The degradation processes appear to make the propagation of a delamination crack in the glass/polyester composite slightly less stable.

The work presented in this paper was undertaken within the research program of the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Ltd., Australia.

REFERENCES

1. Smith, C.S., *Design of Marine Structures in Composite Materials*, Elsevier Applied Science, London, 1990.
2. Mouritz, A.P., Gellert, E., Burchill, P. and Challis, K., "Review of Advanced Composite Structures for Naval Ships and Submarines", *Comp. Struct.*, (In press).
3. Beckwith, S.W. and Hyland, C.R., "FRP and Advanced Composites in the Oilfield", *Comp. Fab.*, August 1998, pp.36.
4. Gutierrez, J., Le Lay, F. and Hoarau, P., "A Study of the Aging of Glass Fibre-Resin Composites in a Marine Environment", In *Nautical Construction with Composite Materials*, ed. Davies, P. and Lemoine, L., Ifremer-Centre De Brest, Paris, 1992.
5. Ellis, B. and Found, M.S., "The Effects of Water Absorption on a Polyester/Chopped Strand Mat Laminate", *Comp.*, 1983, Vol. 26, No. 14, pp.237.
6. Strait, L.H., Karasek, M.L. and Amateau, M.F., "Effects of Seawater Immersion on Impact Resistance of Glass Fiber Reinforced Epoxy Composites", *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1992, Vol. 26, No. 14, pp. 2118.
7. Gellert, E.P. and Turley, D.M., "Seawater Immersion Ageing of Glass-Fibre Reinforced Polymer Laminates for Marine Applications", *Comp.*, 1999, Vol. 30A, pp. 1259.
8. ASTM D790M, "Standard Test Method for Flexural Properties of Unreinforced and Reinforced Plastics and Electrical Insulating Materials", *ASTM Standards and Literature References for Composite Materials*, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1994.
9. ASTM D5528, "Standard Test Method for Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites", *ASTM Standards and Literature References for Composite Materials*, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1994.
10. Liao, K., Schultheisz, C.R., Hunston, D.L. and Brinson, L.C., "Long Term Durability of Fiber Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composite Materials for Infrastructure Applications: A Review", *J. Adv. Mat.*, 1998, pp. 54.
11. Apicella, A., Migliaresi, C., Nicolais, L. and Roccotelli, S., "The water aging of unsturated polyester-based composites: influence of resin chemical structure" *Composites*, 1983, Vol. 14, No. 4, 387-392.
12. Boniard, E., Pethrick, R.A. and Dalze-Job, J., "Studies of water permeation into fibre reinforced composite structures", *Plast. Rubber. Compos. Process. Appl.*, 1998, Vol. 27, No. 4, pp. 206.
13. Seddon, M. Private communication.